

Benchmark Evaluation of a Cannabinoid Drug Interaction Chatbot

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Table S1: Benchmarking Terms and Calculation Formulas

(1) **Accuracy** measures the overall correctness of the system's predictions as a percentage, given by:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Questions}} \times 100$$

where *Number of Correct Predictions* is the count of correct responses, and the *Total Number of Questions* is the dataset size.

(2) **Contextual Precision** evaluates how precise the system is in retrieving more relevant information given the retrieval context from database or web sources, given by:

$$\text{Contextual Precision} = \frac{1}{\text{Number of Relevant Nodes}} \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\text{Number of Relevant Nodes Up to Position } k}{k} \times r_k \right)$$

For each position k up to the total length of the retrieved context n , an LLM-as-a-Judge counts the number of relevant nodes, snippets of the total context, divides by the current position k , and multiplies by a binary relevance indicator r_k (1 if the item at position k is relevant, 0 otherwise).

The relevancy is determined by the LLM through comparisons between the node in retrieved context and expected output. Summing all these values and normalizing by the total number of relevant nodes in the retrieved context yields a weighted cumulative precision, where top nodes carry more weight.

(3) **Contextual Recall** measures the system's ability to retrieve all relevant statements that can be attributed to the retrieval context when compared to the expected response.

$$\text{Contextual Recall} = \frac{\text{Number of Attributable Statements}}{\text{Total Number of Statements}}$$

LLM-as-a Judge utilizes a two-phase process, first identifying the total number of statements in the expected output, then systematically assessing each statement's traceability to snippets of the retrieval context. The resulting value indicates the proportion of statements in the expected output that are traceable to retrieval context.

(4) **Contextual Relevancy** evaluates the proportion of retrieved statements that are contextually aligned with the query, expressed as:

$$\text{Contextual Relevancy} = \frac{\text{Number of Relevant Statements}}{\text{Total Number of Statements}}$$

where *Number of Relevant Statements* is calculated by using LLM-as-a-Judge to analyze each statement in the retrieved context against the user's query to determine relevance. The resulting value represents the proportion of statements in retrieval context that meaningfully contribute to answering the query.

(5) **Answer Relevancy** evaluates how well statements in the generated responses of LLMs align with the user's query, expressed as:

$$\text{Answer Relevancy} = \frac{\text{Number of Relevant Statements}}{\text{Total Number of Statements}}$$

An LLM-as-a-Judge evaluates each statement in the response of a different LLM, determining its relevance to the user's query. The resulting value represents the proportion of statements in actual output of the evaluated LLM that are relevant to the user's input.

(6) **Answer Faithfulness** measures how accurately the system maintains truth and factual consistency based on retrieval context in its outputs, expressed as:

$$\text{Answer Faithfulness} = \frac{\text{Number of Truthful Claims}}{\text{Total Number of Claims}}$$

LLM-as-a-Judge identifies discrete claims from the actual response of the evaluated LLM. Subsequently, the LLM-as-a-Judge evaluates the veracity of each extracted claim by comparing it against the established facts within the retrieval context. The assessment determines the percentage of statements in the evaluated LLM's output that truthfully reflect the retrieval context.

References:

DeepEval - RAG Metrics. DeepEval. Updated April 29th, 2025. Accessed May 5th, 2025, <https://www.deepeval.com/docs/metrics-introduction>

Dowd PA. Accuracy and Precision. In: Daya Sagar BS, Cheng Q, McKinley J, Agterberg F, eds. *Encyclopedia of Mathematical Geosciences*. Springer International Publishing; 2023:1–4.

Table S2: Open Response Answer Faithfulness (AF) and Answer Relevancy (AR) Metrics (Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5)

Metric Score	Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5													
	DDI ^b		CK ^c		MG ^d		A ^e		PM ^f		CB ^g		CM ^h	
	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j
[0, 0.1)	16	2	4	3	-	1	3	-	2	3	1	-	3	2
[0.1, 0.2)	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	1
[0.2, 0.3)	2	-	2	2	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	4	-	4
[0.3, 0.4)	6	-	2	5	-	-	2	1	1	3	2	1	-	3
[0.4, 0.5)	1	-	1	3	1	-	-	1	3	8	1	1	1	2
[0.5, 0.6)	27	2	7	8	2	5	8	6	4	20	1	9	4	12
[0.6, 0.7)	24	3	11	11	5	5	6	7	9	16	10	8	10	8
[0.7, 0.8)	11	3	7	18	6	3	10	9	6	22	6	14	13	8
[0.8, 0.9)	20	6	30	31	11	13	9	6	25	57	8	12	14	13
[0.9, 1.0]	173	264	201	183	75	71	97	104	222	140	115	94	128	120

Legend:

^aMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)

^bDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)

^cClinical Knowledge (CK) MMLU^a

^dMedical Genetics (MG) MMLU^a

^eAnatomy (A) MMLU^a

^fProfessional Medicine (PM) MMLU^a

^gCollege Biology (CB) MMLU^a

^hCollege Medicine (CM) MMLU^a

ⁱAnswer Faithfulness (AF)

^jAnswer Relevancy (AR)

Table S2 presents a comprehensive evaluation of Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5 model's performance across various medical domains using two key metrics: Answer Faithfulness (AF) and Answer Relevancy (AR), distributed across different score ranges.

Notably, the data is concentrated at the top ranges for Answer Relevancy (AR) on all metrics except MMLU Professional Medicine (PM). There was a larger distribution of responses at the moderate performance range (0.5-0.8) for MMLU Professional Medicine Answer Relevancy(AR).

For Answer Faithfulness (AF), the same trends manifested; however, a larger distribution of responses concentrated at the moderate performance range for cannabinoid DDI Answer Faithfulness (AF).

Table S3: Open Response Answer Faithfulness (AF) and Answer Relevancy (AR) Metrics (Gemma-2-9B-IT + gte-large-en-v1.5)

Metric Score	Gemma-2-9B-IT + gte-large-en-v1.5													
	DDI ^b		CK ^c		MG ^d		A ^e		PM ^f		CB ^g		CM ^h	
	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j
[0, 0.1)	4	-	3	4	2	-	7	1	-	1	1	3	5	-
[0.1, 0.2)	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
[0.2, 0.3)	-	-	-	3	-	-	1	2	-	2	-	1	-	6
[0.3, 0.4)	2	1	2	4	-	3	-	-	-	2	2	1	-	-
[0.4, 0.5)	-	2	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	4	-	1	-	-
[0.5, 0.6)	12	5	3	10	2	5	-	3	2	6	3	10	7	7
[0.6, 0.7)	15	8	8	17	4	7	3	8	4	25	6	11	3	12
[0.7, 0.8)	12	4	7	15	3	4	3	5	7	41	7	10	5	11
[0.8, 0.9)	9	9	14	23	4	9	3	7	25	50	8	13	9	16
[0.9, 1.0]	226	251	228	188	85	70	118	109	234	141	117	93	144	120

Legend:

^aMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)

^bDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)

^cClinical Knowledge (CK) MMLU^a

^dMedical Genetics (MG) MMLU^a

^eAnatomy (A) MMLU^a

^fProfessional Medicine (PM) MMLU^a

^gCollege Biology (CB) MMLU^a

^hCollege Medicine (CM) MMLU^a

ⁱAnswer Faithfulness (AF)

^jAnswer Relevancy (AR)

Table S3 shows the evaluation of Gemma-2-9B-IT + gte-large-en-v1.5 with context on Answer Faithfulness (AF) and Answer Relevancy (AR). A similar pattern to the Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct model is apparent for Gemma-2-9B-IT’s Answer Relevancy (AR).

Again, MMLU Professional Medicine (PM) had a larger number of responses concentrated around the moderate performance range. The Answer Faithfulness (AF) of Gemma-2-9B-IT (247 responses scored greater than 0.7) was stronger for the cannabinoid DDI dataset than Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct (204 responses scored greater than 0.7).

Table S4: Open Response Answer Faithfulness (AF) and Answer Relevancy (AR) Metrics (Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5)

Metric Score	Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5													
	DDI ^b		CK ^c		MG ^d		A ^e		PM ^f		CB ^g		CM ^h	
	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j	AF ⁱ	AR ^j
[0, 0.1)	2	2	2	4	2	2	-	2	-	1	2	7	1	3
[0.1, 0.2)	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-
[0.2, 0.3)	1	-	-	2	-	1	-	1	-	3	-	1	4	2
[0.3, 0.4)	2	-	-	2	1	-	2	2	1	2	-	1	2	1
[0.4, 0.5)	3	-	-	2	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	1	1	2
[0.5, 0.6)	5	3	11	5	1	4	7	4	5	10	4	7	5	8
[0.6, 0.7)	11	1	11	11	1	4	12	5	6	7	8	8	6	7
[0.7, 0.8)	17	1	11	15	5	8	4	5	10	23	6	10	4	14
[0.8, 0.9)	27	9	16	16	7	4	13	8	29	53	12	12	13	13
[0.9, 1.0]	212	256	214	207	83	75	97	108	221	170	112	96	137	123

Legend:

^aMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)

^bDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)

^cClinical Knowledge (CK) MMLU^a

^dMedical Genetics (MG) MMLU^a

^eAnatomy (A) MMLU^a

^fProfessional Medicine (PM) MMLU^a

^gCollege Biology (CB) MMLU^a

^hCollege Medicine (CM) MMLU^a

ⁱAnswer Faithfulness (AF)

^jAnswer Relevancy (AR)

Table S4 shows the evaluation of Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct with context on Answer Faithfulness (AF) and Answer Relevancy (AR). Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct demonstrates strong performance with the most responses being scored as greater than 0.7 for both metrics across the datasets.

For the cannabinoid DDI dataset, Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct had the highest number of responses scored greater than 0.9 for Answer Relevancy (AR). Moreover, the Answer Faithfulness (AF) of Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct was high (256 responses scored greater than 0.7) compared to the Gemma-2-9B-IT and Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct models.

Table S5: GTE-large-en-v1.5 Routing Contextual Precision Metrics

Metric Score	Contextual Precision						
	DDI ^b	CK ^c	MG ^d	A ^e	PM ^f	CB ^g	CM ^h
[0, 0.1)	11	122	34	27	153	46	87
[0.1, 0.2)	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
[0.2, 0.3)	-	37	17	17	53	25	17
[0.3, 0.4)	-	23	2	20	10	9	10
[0.4, 0.5)	-	6	3	6	2	6	-
[0.5, 0.6)	-	20	10	18	9	17	17
[0.6, 0.7)	-	5	1	-	-	1	3
[0.7, 0.8)	-	4	4	5	8	4	2
[0.8, 0.9)	-	14	5	7	8	6	9
[0.9, 1.0]	269	33	24	35	29	30	28

Legend:^aMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)^bDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)^cClinical Knowledge (CK) MMLU^a^dMedical Genetics (MG) MMLU^a^eAnatomy (A) MMLU^a^fProfessional Medicine (PM) MMLU^a^gCollege Biology (CB) MMLU^a^hCollege Medicine (CM) MMLU^a

Table S5 presents the Contextual Precision scores of context attained with gte-large-en-v1.5 serving as the routing model. For the cannabinoid DDI dataset, 269 instances of context scored greater than 0.9. The 11 cases of the lowest metric score arise from the challenge of the fuzzy

string-matching system in retrieving the correct context for drugs with similar names. The analysis revealed significant contextual precision deficiencies across medical domains, with low metric scores documented in MMLU Clinical Knowledge (CK) with 122 instances, MMLU Professional Medicine (PM) with 153 instances, and MMLU College Medicine (CM) with 87 instances. These limitations were primarily due to the abbreviated nature of webpage snippet summaries, which lacked comprehensive contextual information.

Table S6: GTE-large-en-v1.5 Routing Contextual Relevancy Metrics

Metric Score	Contextual Relevancy						
	DDI ^b	CK ^c	MG ^d	A ^e	PM ^f	CB ^g	CM ^h
[0, 0.1)	2	69	27	17	120	36	60
[0.1, 0.2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.2, 0.3)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.3, 0.4)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.4, 0.5)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.5, 0.6)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.6, 0.7)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.7, 0.8)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.8, 0.9)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[0.9, 1.0]	278	196	73	118	152	108	113

Legend:^aMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)^bDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)^cClinical Knowledge (CK) MMLU^a^dMedical Genetics (MG) MMLU^a^eAnatomy (A) MMLU^a^fProfessional Medicine (PM) MMLU^a^gCollege Biology (CB) MMLU^a^hCollege Medicine (CM)

Table S6 presents the contextual relevancy scores of context attained with gte-large-en-v1.5 serving as the routing model. The context of the cannabinoid DDI dataset was highly relevant

with 278/280 instances scored greater than 0.9. MMLU Medical genetics (MG) with 73 instances, MMLU Anatomy (A) with 118 instances, MMLU Clinical Knowledge (CK) with 196 instances and MMLU College Biology (CB) with 108 instances each had more than 70% of context instances scored greater than 0.9. Again, MMLU College Medicine (CM) and MMLU Professional Medicine (PM) had a greater number of lower scores (below 0.1).

Table S7: GTE-large-en-v1.5 Routing Contextual Recall Metrics

Metric Score	Contextual Recall						
	DDI ^b	CK ^c	MG ^d	A ^e	PM ^f	CB ^g	CM ^h
[0, 0.1)	11	135	42	45	206	62	103
[0.1, 0.2)	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
[0.2, 0.3)	-	-	1	4	4	3	1
[0.3, 0.4)	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
[0.4, 0.5)	-	2	1	1	5	1	-
[0.5, 0.6)	1	-	4	2	8	2	4
[0.6, 0.7)	-	3	1	1	1	4	4
[0.7, 0.8)	-	3	1	-	-	-	1
[0.8, 0.9)	-	-	-	1	-	2	2
[0.9, 1.0]	268	122	50	79	47	70	58

Legend:^aMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)^bDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)^cClinical Knowledge (CK) MMLU^a^dMedical Genetics (MG) MMLU^a^eAnatomy (A) MMLU^a^fProfessional Medicine (PM) MMLU^a^gCollege Biology (CB) MMLU^a^hCollege Medicine (CM) MMLU^a

Table S7 presents the contextual recall analysis using gte-large-en-v1.5 as the routing model and reveals distinct patterns across different medical datasets. The contextual recall metric

compares retrieval context against the expected output. Strong context-output alignment was observed in cannabinoid drug interactions, medical genetics, anatomy and college biology.

In contrast, clinical knowledge, professional medicine, and college medicine datasets showed a higher proportion of low-scoring contexts (< 0.1) compared to high-scoring ones (> 0.9).